

Supplementary Material for: The emergence of division of labor through decentralized social sanctioning

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1 Sensitivity analysis on the learning rate (α)

We tested the performance of the social norms evolved for learning rate ($\alpha = 0.1$) on the learning processes with high ($\alpha = 0.5$) and low ($\alpha = 0.01$) settings. The results are shown in Figure 1. Based on the results, social norms that are evolved for $\alpha = 0.1$ lead to similar but slow learning processes in case of low learning rate, however, they do not lead to similar or better performance when the learning rate is high. On the other hand, when social norms are evolved particularly for low and high learning rates, shown in Figure 2, we observe the emergence of social norms that can produce similar results.

Figure 1: How sensitive is the performance of the emerged social norms when ($\alpha = 0.1$) to low or high learning rates ($\alpha = 0.01$ and $\alpha = 0.5$)? In most cases, a lower learning rate ($\alpha = 0.01$) leads to similar results with a slower learning speed. On the other hand, in most cases, a higher learning rate ($\alpha = 0.5$) does not lead to a better/similar performance. This may be due to a greedy learning process where the individuals get stuck on a suboptimal role distribution without much exploration.

2 Sensitivity analysis on the parameters of the cultural evolution

In Figure 3, we show the results of evolutionary processes that use different sets of parameters to adjust the intensity of producing variation in social sanctioning rules. We define three parameters (to correspond to low, medium and high values) to test the effect of four variables: mutation probability ($mp = \{0.1, 0.5, 0.9\}$), mutation rate ($mr = \{0.1, 0.5, 1\}$), rule addi-

Figure 2: when social norms are evolved particularly for low and high learning rates, they can produce similar results.

tion probability ($rap = \{0.1, 0.5, 0.9\}$) and rule deletion probability ($rdp = \{0.1, 0.5, 0.9\}$). All the combinations of these parameters yields to 81 independent social sanctioning rule evolution processes. We ran 30 independent evolutionary processes for all 81 parameter combinations on the settlement maintenance game with $wa = 6$ and $P = 1$ settings.

Firstly, although, the parameter settings are ranked based on the average group payoff they received over these 30 runs (see Figure 3 (B)), top performing parameter setting does not show significantly different results relative to the following top 20 best ranked parameter settings.

Figure 3: Sensitivity analysis of the evolutionary process in respect to the parameters used to produce social sanctioning rule variations. Parameters used for generating variation in social sanctioning rules: mutation probability (mp), mutation rate (mr), rule addition probability (rap), rule deletion probability (rdp). Overall, parameters that modify sanctioning values with a lower probability and higher variance (e.g. $mp \leq 0.5$ and $mr \geq 0.5$) or higher probability and lower variance (e.g. $mp \geq 0.5$ and $mr \leq 0.5$), and high probability of adding new rules (e.g. $rap \geq 0.5$), and low probability of deleting rules (e.g. $rdp \leq 0.5$) achieved higher average group payoffs at the end of the evolutionary processes.

3 Evolved social norms and the effect of the complexity regularization

Settlement maintenance, Environment 1 ($w_a = 0, P = 0$)

A. Evolved social norms in independent cultural evolutionary processes depending on λ

$\lambda = 0$

ID	Rules that constitute a social norm
1	(1) Cleaner ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.71 (2) Cleaner ought to discourage Forager by -1.74 (3) Cleaner ought to encourage Hunter by 3.53 (4) Cleaner ought to discourage Soldier by -1.76 (5) Forager ought to encourage Cleaner by 4.22 (6) Forager ought to encourage Forager by 2.04 (7) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 3.00 (8) Forager ought to discourage Soldier by -0.27 (9) Hunter ought to discourage Cleaner by -0.44 (10) Hunter ought to encourage Forager by 0.12 (11) Hunter ought to encourage Hunter by 3.69 (12) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 2.61 (13) Soldier ought to discourage Cleaner by -0.14 (14) Soldier ought to discourage Forager by -3.36 (15) Soldier ought to encourage Hunter by 2.55 (16) Soldier ought to encourage Soldier by 0.03
2	(1) Cleaner ought to discourage Forager by -0.36 (2) Cleaner ought to encourage Hunter by 1.13 (3) Cleaner ought to encourage Soldier by 1.03 (4) Forager ought to discourage Cleaner by -0.89 (5) Forager ought to encourage Forager by 0.48 (6) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 1.67 (7) Hunter ought to discourage Hunter by -0.57 (8) Soldier ought to encourage Soldier by 0.39

$\lambda = 0.2$

ID	Rules that constitute a social norm
1	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 2.21
2	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 1.82
3	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 2.56
4	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 2.03
5	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 0.56
6	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 0.14
7	(1) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -2.88
8	(1) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -0.96
9	(1) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -2.03
10	(1) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -1.94

B. Average payoff of the best 5 evolved social norms during the lifetime learning process of division of labor

C. Emerged spatial role distributions

Settlement maintenance, Environment 2 ($wa = 6, P = 0$)

A. Evolved social norms in independent cultural evolutionary processes depending on λ

$\lambda = 0$		$\lambda = 0.2$	
ID	Rules that constitute a social norm	ID	Rules that constitute a social norm
1	(1) Cleaner ought to discourage Cleaner by -1.44	1	(1) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.60
	(2) Cleaner ought to discourage Forager by -0.19		(2) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -1.45
	(3) Cleaner ought to discourage Soldier by -0.11	2	(1) Cleaner ought to discourage Hunter by -0.62
	(4) Forager ought to encourage Cleaner by 1.48		(2) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 0.96
	(5) Forager ought to discourage Forager by -0.27	3	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 2.56
	(6) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 1.09		(2) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.62
	(7) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.54	4	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 0.93
	(8) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -2.36		(2) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.57
	(9) Hunter ought to encourage Hunter by 1.03	5	(1) Cleaner ought to discourage Hunter by -0.64
	(10) Hunter ought to discourage Soldier by -0.48		(2) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 2.74
	(11) Soldier ought to discourage Cleaner by -2.39	6	(1) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.63
	(12) Soldier ought to discourage Forager by -0.54		(2) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -1.45
	(13) Soldier ought to encourage Hunter by 0.49	7	(1) Cleaner ought to discourage Hunter by -0.64
	(14) Soldier ought to encourage Soldier by 0.84		(2) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 2.24
2	(1) Cleaner ought to discourage Forager by -1.20	8	(1) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.61
	(2) Forager ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.63		(2) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -2.52
	(3) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.53	9	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 2.35
	(4) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -1.98		(2) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.58
	(5) Hunter ought to encourage Hunter by 6	10	(1) Cleaner ought to discourage Hunter by -0.61
	(6) Soldier ought to discourage Cleaner by -0.56		(2) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -2.38
	(7) Soldier ought to discourage Soldier by -1.20		

B. Average payoff of the best 5 evolved social norms during the lifetime learning process of division of labor

C. Emerged spatial role distributions

Settlement maintenance, Environment 3 ($w_a = 0, P = 1$)

A. Evolved social norms in independent cultural evolutionary processes depending on λ

$\lambda = 0$		$\lambda = 0.2$	
ID	Rules that constitute a social norm	ID	Rules that constitute a social norm
1	(1) Cleaner ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.17	1	(1) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -0.54
	(2) Cleaner ought to encourage Forager by 1.66		(2) Soldier ought to discourage Hunter by -0.25
	(3) Cleaner ought to discourage Hunter by -0.61	2	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 1.19
	(4) Cleaner ought to encourage Soldier by 1.2212		(2) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 0.27
	(5) Forager ought to discourage Cleaner by -0.7215	3	(1) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -1.76
	(6) Forager ought to discourage Forager by -1.4371		(2) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 0.24
	(7) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 1.7733	4	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 1.99
	(8) Forager ought to discourage Soldier by -4.4065		(2) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 0.28
	(9) Hunter ought to discourage Cleaner by -1.95	5	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 2.81
	(10) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -1.17		(2) Soldier ought to discourage Hunter by -0.30
	(11) Hunter ought to encourage Hunter by 5.1159	6	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 1.96
	(12) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 0.50		(2) Soldier ought to discourage Hunter by -0.22
	(13) Soldier ought to discourage Cleaner by -1.52	7	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 2.12
	(14) Soldier ought to discourage Forager by -2.93		(2) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 0.32
	(15) Soldier ought to discourage Soldier by -3.65	8	(1) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -0.47
	(2) Soldier ought to discourage Hunter by -0.19		
2	(1) Forager ought to discourage Hunter by -0.68	9	(1) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 2.3
	(2) Forager ought to encourage Soldier by 1.89		(2) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 0.25
	(3) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -2.75	10	(1) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -2.35
	(4) Soldier ought to discourage Hunter by -0.28		(2) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 0.34
	(5) Soldier ought to encourage Soldier by 0.79		

B. Average payoff of the best 5 emerged social norms during the lifetime learning process of division of labor

C. Emerged spatial role distributions

Settlement maintenance, Environment 4 ($w\alpha = 3.2, P = 0.5$)

A. Evolved social norms in independent cultural evolutionary processes depending on λ

$\lambda = 0$		$\lambda = 0.2$	
ID	Rules that constitute a social norm	ID	Rules that constitute a social norm
1	(1) Cleaner ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.07	1	(1) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.44
	(2) Cleaner ought to encourage Forager by 0.30		(2) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -0.98
	(3) Cleaner ought to discourage Hunter by -1.26		(3) Soldier ought to discourage Hunter by -0.39
	(4) Cleaner ought to discourage Soldier by -0.40	2	(1) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.57
	(5) Forager ought to discourage Cleaner by -0.50		(2) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -2.28
	(6) Forager ought to discourage Forager by -1.94		(3) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 0.42
	(7) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 2.69		3
	(8) Forager ought to discourage Soldier by -2.00	(2) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -1.86	
	(9) Hunter ought to discourage Cleaner by -1.04	(3) Soldier ought to discourage Hunter by -0.31	
	(10) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -2.18	2	(1) Cleaner ought to discourage Hunter by -0.46
(11) Hunter ought to discourage Hunter by -1.08	(2) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -1.30		
(12) Hunter ought to discourage Soldier by -4.47	(3) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 0.32		
(13) Soldier ought to discourage Cleaner by -0.16	5		(1) Cleaner ought to discourage Hunter by -5.29
(14) Soldier ought to discourage Forager by -0.29			(2) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 0.77
(15) Soldier ought to discourage Hunter by -0.49			(3) Hunter ought to discourage Cleaner by -2.73
(16) Soldier ought to discourage Soldier by -2.055		(4) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 3.84	
2	(1) Cleaner ought to encourage Forager by 0.244	6	(1) Cleaner ought to discourage Hunter by -0.09
	(2) Cleaner ought to discourage Hunter by -0.83		(2) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.38
	(3) Forager ought to discourage Cleaner by -0.81		(3) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -0.64
	(4) Forager ought to discourage Hunter by -0.22		(4) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 0.33
	(5) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -1.10	7	(1) Cleaner ought to discourage Hunter by -0.38
	(6) Hunter ought to discourage Hunter by -1.43		(2) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -1.17
	(7) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 0.24		(3) Hunter ought to encourage Hunter by 2.15
	(8) Soldier ought to discourage Cleaner by -2.76		(4) Soldier ought to discourage Hunter by -0.37
	(9) Soldier ought to encourage Forager by 1.85		
	(10) Soldier ought to discourage Soldier by -1.61		

B. Average payoff of the best 5 emerged social norms during the lifetime learning process of division of labor

C. Emerged spatial role distributions

Settlement maintenance, Environment 5 ($wa = 6, P = 1$)

A. Evolved social norms in independent cultural evolutionary processes depending on λ

$\lambda = 0$

$\lambda = 0.2$

ID	Rules that constitute a social norm	ID	Rules that constitute a social norm
1	(1) Cleaner ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.02 (2) Cleaner ought to encourage Forager by 0.04 (3) Cleaner ought to discourage Hunter by -5.54 (4) Forager ought to encourage Cleaner by 3.74 (5) Forager ought to encourage Forager by 0.17 (6) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 2.34 (7) Forager ought to discourage Soldier by -3.29 (8) Hunter ought to discourage Cleaner by -2.73 (9) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -1.24 (10) Hunter ought to encourage Hunter by 1.19 (11) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 3.75 (12) Soldier ought to discourage Forager by -3.15 (13) Soldier ought to encourage Hunter by 6 (14) Soldier ought to discourage Soldier by -1.67	1	(1) Cleaner ought to encourage Soldier by 1.31 (2) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 0.45 (3) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -1.71 (4) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 0.21
2	(1) Cleaner ought to discourage Cleaner by -0.97 (2) Cleaner ought to encourage Forager by 4.90 (3) Cleaner ought to encourage Hunter by 1.78 (4) Cleaner ought to discourage Soldier by -2.97 (5) Forager ought to discourage Cleaner by -5.98 (6) Forager ought to encourage Forager by 4.00 (7) Forager ought to encourage Hunter by 1.10 (8) Forager ought to encourage Soldier by 5.77 (9) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 3.2 (10) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -2.69 (11) Hunter ought to encourage Hunter by 0.12 (12) Hunter ought to discourage Soldier by -1.84 (13) Soldier ought to discourage Cleaner by -6 (14) Soldier ought to discourage Forager by -1.66 (15) Soldier ought to discourage Hunter by -6 (16) Soldier ought to encourage Soldier by 0.57	2	(1) Cleaner ought to encourage Hunter by 1.15 (2) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 3.13 (3) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -0.54 (4) Hunter ought to discourage Soldier by -1.52 (5) Soldier ought to discourage Hunter by -4.52
		3	(1) Cleaner ought to encourage Soldier by 3.91 (2) Hunter ought to encourage Cleaner by 4.22 (3) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -2.25 (4) Hunter ought to encourage Hunter by 2.01 (5) Soldier ought to discourage Hunter by -0.11
		4	(1) Cleaner ought to discourage Hunter by -6 (2) Hunter ought to discourage Cleaner by -1.51 (3) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -1.18 (4) Soldier ought to encourage Cleaner by 3.44 (5) Soldier ought to discourage Hunter by -4.61
		5	(1) Cleaner ought to discourage Hunter by -5.04 (2) Hunter ought to discourage Cleaner by -3.32 (3) Hunter ought to discourage Forager by -0.46 (4) Hunter ought to encourage Hunter by 0.95 (5) Hunter ought to encourage Soldier by 6 (6) Soldier ought to encourage Hunter by 3.78

B. Average payoff of the best 5 emerged social norms during the lifetime learning process of division of labor

C. Emerged spatial role distributions

Roles: ■ Cleaner (C) ■ Forager (F) ■ Hunter (H) ■ Soldier (S)

Common pasture, Environment 2 ($w = 0.5, c = 0$)

A. Evolved social norms in independent cultural evolutionary processes depending on λ

$\lambda = 0$		$\lambda = 0.2$	
ID	Rules that constitute a social norm	ID	Rules that constitute a social norm
1	(1) Greedy ought to discourage Greedy by -0.37 (2) Greedy ought to discourage Considerate by -0.042 (3) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -6 (4) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -0.91 (5) Worker ought to discourage Greedy by -0.11	1	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 2.50 (2) Considerate ought to encourage Considerate by 4.60
2	(1) Greedy ought to discourage Greedy by -0.92 (2) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 3.45 (3) Greedy ought to discourage Worker by -0.58 (4) Considerate ought to encourage Greedy by 0.22 (5) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -4.86 (6) Considerate ought to discourage Worker by -1.31 (7) Worker ought to discourage Greedy by -2.66 (8) Worker ought to discourage Considerate by -0.32 (9) Worker ought to discourage Worker by -4.47	2	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 6 (2) Considerate ought to encourage Considerate by 1.09
3	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Greedy by 1.03 (2) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -1.71 (3) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -4.85 (4) Worker ought to discourage Considerate by -0.24	3	(1) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -2.53 (2) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -2.21
		4	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 3.48 (2) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -1.69
		5	(1) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -3.67 (2) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -1.94
		6	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 6 (2) Considerate ought to encourage Considerate by 1.05
		7	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 3.72 (2) Considerate ought to encourage Considerate by 3.99
		8	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 3.33 (2) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -1.31
		9	(1) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -3.56 (2) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -1.67
		10	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 2.51 (2) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -2.08

B. Average payoff of the best 5 emerged social norms during the lifetime learning process of division of labor

C. Emerged spatial role distributions

Common pasture, Environment 3 ($w = 0, c = 0.5$)

A. Evolved social norms in independent cultural evolutionary processes depending on λ

$\lambda = 0$		$\lambda = 0.2$	
ID	Rules that constitute a social norm	ID	Rules that constitute a social norm
1	(1) Greedy ought to discourage Greedy by -1.92 (2) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 0.91 (3) Greedy ought to encourage Worker by 1.85 (4) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -1.10 (5) Considerate ought to encourage Considerate by 0.33 (6) Considerate ought to encourage Worker by 1.51 (7) Worker ought to discourage Greedy by -1.82 (8) Worker ought to discourage Considerate by -0.86 (9) Worker ought to discourage Worker by -5.82	1	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Worker by 1.85 (2) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -2.69 (3) Considerate ought to encourage Worker by 1.21 (4) Worker ought to discourage Considerate by -3.37
	2	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Greedy by 0.049 (2) Greedy ought to discourage Considerate by -0.45 (3) Greedy ought to encourage Worker by 0.95 (4) Considerate ought to encourage Greedy by 2.93 (5) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -1.23 (6) Considerate ought to encourage Worker by 0.57 (7) Worker ought to discourage Greedy by -1.87 (8) Worker ought to discourage Considerate by -2.67 (9) Worker ought to encourage Worker by 0.01	2
			3
		4	(1) Greedy ought to discourage Considerate by -0.12 (2) Greedy ought to encourage Worker by 1.50 (3) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -0.003 (4) Considerate ought to encourage Considerate by 0.06 (5) Considerate ought to encourage Worker by 0.68 (6) Worker ought to discourage Greedy by -5.06

B. Average payoff of the best 5 emerged social norms during the lifetime learning process of division of labor

C. Emerged spatial role distributions

Common pasture, Environment 4 ($w = 0.27, c = 0.27$)

A. Evolved social norms in independent cultural evolutionary processes depending on λ

$\lambda = 0$		$\lambda = 0.2$	
ID	Rules that constitute a social norm	ID	Rules that constitute a social norm
1	(1) Greedy ought to discourage Greedy by -1.10 (2) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 1.91 (3) Greedy ought to encourage Worker by 2.07 (4) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -5.72 (5) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -0.24 (6) Considerate ought to encourage Worker by 3.36 (7) Worker ought to discourage Greedy by -0.43 (8) Worker ought to encourage Considerate by 3.04 (9) Worker ought to discourage Worker by -3.17	1	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Worker by 2.69 (2) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -1.68 (3) Considerate ought to encourage Worker by 2.52
2	(1) Greedy ought to discourage Greedy by -0.91 (2) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 2.54 (3) Greedy ought to encourage Worker by 3.66 (4) Considerate ought to encourage Considerate by 5.55 (5) Considerate ought to encourage Worker by 2.53 (6) Worker ought to discourage Greedy by -1.53 (7) Worker ought to discourage Considerate by -5.61	2	(1) Greedy ought to discourage Greedy by -2.96 (2) Greedy ought to encourage Worker by 3.39 (3) Considerate ought to encourage Worker by 3.93
3	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Greedy by 0.473 (2) Greedy ought to discourage Worker by -0.17 (3) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -2.24 (4) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -0.15 (5) Considerate ought to encourage Worker by 3.09 (6) Worker ought to discourage Greedy by -1.78 (7) Worker ought to encourage Considerate by 4.20 (8) Worker ought to discourage Worker by -2.74	3	(1) Considerate ought to encourage Greedy by 3.75 (2) Considerate ought to encourage Worker by 2.55 (3) Worker ought to discourage Greedy by -4.87
		4	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 0.93 (2) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -5.97 (3) Considerate ought to discourage Worker by -1.90 (4) Worker ought to discourage Considerate by -4.59
		5	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Greedy by 0.33 (2) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 2.52 (3) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -1.63 (4) Considerate ought to discourage Worker by -1.06 (5) Worker ought to discourage Greedy by -6 (6) Worker ought to discourage Considerate by -3.86
		6	(1) Greedy ought to discourage Greedy by -1.71 (2) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 3.77 (3) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -1.72 (4) Worker ought to discourage Greedy by -1.17 (5) Worker ought to discourage Considerate by -6

B. Average payoff of the best 5 emerged social norms during the lifetime learning process of division of labor

C. Emerged spatial role distributions

Common pasture, Environment 5 ($w = 0.5, c = 0.5$)

A. Evolved social norms in independent cultural evolutionary processes depending on λ

$\lambda = 0$		$\lambda = 0.2$	
ID	Rules that constitute a social norm	ID	Rules that constitute a social norm
1	(1) Greedy ought to discourage Greedy by -3.66	1	(1) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -3.63
	(2) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 2.86		(2) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -1.93
	(3) Greedy ought to encourage Worker by 0.19	2	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 6
	(4) Considerate ought to encourage Greedy by 0.97		(2) Considerate ought to encourage Considerate by 1.06
	(5) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -1.71	3	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 5.61
	(6) Considerate ought to discourage Worker by -1.96		(2) Considerate ought to encourage Considerate by 0.92
	(7) Worker ought to discourage Greedy by -6	4	(1) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -3.39
	(8) Worker ought to encourage Considerate by 3.36		(2) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -1.28
	(9) Worker ought to encourage Worker by 0.33	5	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 3.56
2	(1) Greedy ought to discourage Greedy by -0.40		(2) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -1.5
	(2) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 3.81	6	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Greedy by 0.48
	(3) Greedy ought to encourage Worker by 0.62		(2) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 6
	(4) Considerate ought to encourage Greedy by 0.47	(3) Considerate ought to encourage Considerate by 1.09	
	(5) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -3.33	7	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 5.85
	(6) Considerate ought to discourage Worker by -0.08		(2) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -0.86
	(7) Worker ought to discourage Greedy by -2.36	8	(1) Greedy ought to discourage Greedy by -5.35
	(8) Worker ought to encourage Considerate by 4.73		(2) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 3.34
	(9) Worker ought to encourage Worker by 0.21	(3) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -2.91	
3	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Greedy by 5.88	9	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Worker by 3.34
	(2) Greedy ought to discourage Considerate by -0.58		(2) Considerate ought to encourage Worker by 1.25
	(3) Considerate ought to discourage Greedy by -4.51	10	(1) Greedy ought to encourage Considerate by 3.57
	(4) Considerate ought to discourage Considerate by -4.89		(2) Considerate ought to encourage Considerate by 2.06
	(5) Considerate ought to discourage Worker by -1.42		
	(6) Worker ought to discourage Greedy by -2.21		
	(7) Worker ought to encourage Worker by 0.10		

B. Average payoff of the best 5 emerged social norms during the lifetime learning process of division of labor

C. Emerged spatial role distributions

